

1 Heavy metal biosorption by Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS)
2 recovered from anammox granular sludge

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15 **Abstract**

16 The recovery and conversion of Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS) from sewage
17 sludge into bio-based commodities might improve the economics and environmental
18 sustainability of wastewater treatment. The present study explores the feasibility to
19 valorize EPS from anammox granular waste sludge as biosorbents for the removal of
20 heavy metals commonly found in wastewaters both of municipal and industrial origins
21 (lead, copper, nickel, zinc). Different adsorption pathways were detected comparing
22 pristine granules and extracted EPS for their metal-binding ability. Single-metal
23 biosorption tests disclosed adsorption capacities equivalent or higher than well-

24 established adsorbent media (84.9, 52.8, 21.7 and 7.4 mg/gTS_{EPS} and 103.7, 36.1, 48.2
25 and 49.8 mg/gTS_{granules} for Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺, respectively, at 500 mg/L initial
26 metal concentration), suggesting the feasibility to valorize anammox EPS and/or
27 granules for the treatment of heavy metal-contaminated wastewaters. Anammox EPS
28 exhibited high adsorption capacities in multi-metal aqueous systems, proving to be
29 promising biosorbents for the treatment of effluents contaminated by several heavy
30 metals. Combining a series of spectroscopic techniques, a detailed description of the
31 EPS/heavy metal interaction at the molecular level was provided, proposing a
32 mechanistic hypothesis for metal biosorption based on a combination of electrostatic
33 interaction, ion exchange, complexation, and precipitation.

34

35 **Keywords:** extracellular polymeric substances; anammox granular waste sludge;
36 resource recovery; heavy metals; biosorption.

37

38 1. Introduction

39 Autotrophic biological processes based on the metabolism of anaerobic ammonium
40 oxidizing bacteria (anammox) allow removing ammonium from wastewater with
41 significant savings in terms of energy spent for oxygen supply (-60%) and organic
42 carbon supply (-100%); in addition, the production of excess sludge is reduced (-90%)
43 compared to conventional nitrification/denitrification processes (Hu et al., 2013; Lotti et
44 al., 2019a). For these reasons, anammox-based technologies are becoming the new
45 standard for the treatment of nitrogen-rich wastewaters of municipal and industrial
46 origins (Lackner et al., 2014). Anammox bacteria easily form granules (i.e., self-

47 aggregated biofilms) without the presence of inert carriers. Thanks to these features,
48 granular systems are characterized by higher biomass concentrations and volumetric
49 conversion rates, if compared to flocculent or biofilm on carriers systems and as a
50 matter of fact treat more than 50% of the total N-load handled with anammox
51 technologies worldwide (Lackner et al., 2014). Anammox processes are currently
52 applied in full-scale side stream installations for the treatment of reject waters of
53 anaerobic digestion. Considering the worldwide increasing trend of biogas production
54 (Scarlat et al., 2018), the N-load treated in anammox plants, and therefore the anammox
55 excess sludge production, is expected to increase in the future at a similar rate:
56 strategies for the efficient anammox granular waste sludge management are therefore
57 demanded (Feng et al., 2020). As in conventional biofilms, in anammox granules
58 microorganisms are embedded in a matrix of hydrated extracellular polymeric
59 substances (EPS) (Flemming and Wingender, 2010; Seviour et al., 2019, 2012). EPS,
60 which account for up to 90% w/w of the organics in biofilm (Flemming et al., 2007), are
61 a complex mixture of polysaccharides, proteins (structural proteins or exoenzymes),
62 nucleic acids, (phospho)lipids, humic substances and intercellular polymers (Flemming
63 et al., 2016). Anammox EPS are mostly composed by proteinaceous material (>60%),
64 with a low content (about 7%) of carbohydrates (Lotti et al., 2019a). Lotti et al.
65 (2019b) observed the presence of amyloid-like fibrils in anammox EPS that possibly
66 have a structural function in biofilms (Flemming et al., 2007; Taglialegna et al., 2017;
67 Lin et al., 2018). The conversion of EPS recovered from waste sludge into bio-based
68 commodities is getting increasing attention as appealing route to enhance sustainability
69 and economics of wastewater treatment (Lin et al., 2015), promoting the development
70 of circular economy chains. Waste sludge-derived EPS might be valorized for their

71 metal sorption properties, as demonstrated in many studies (Guibaud et al., 2012; Li et
72 al., 2017; Wei et al., 2016, 2019). However, anammox EPS have not yet been
73 thoroughly addressed for their metal-binding ability.

74 The rapid industrial development and accelerating urbanization resulted in the
75 production of various toxic substances, among which heavy metals have become an
76 issue of great concern, due to their toxicity, non-biodegradability and potential to
77 bioaccumulate in human body and food chain (He and Chen, 2014; Wang et al., 2018).

78 Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), not specifically designed to remove heavy
79 metals, may require the optimization of conventional treatment processes or the
80 implementation of advanced treatment technologies (Hargreaves et al., 2018) to be
81 consistent with the current environmental regulation that imposes improved quality of
82 both end-products of wastewater treatment (i.e., effluent and sludge). Land application
83 of treated sewage sludge, worldwide considered as an economically and
84 environmentally sustainable solution for sludge management (Cantinho et al., 2016),
85 can be compromised by the high level of metals often retained in the excess sludge. If
86 compared to many conventional treatment systems (e.g. chemical precipitation, ion
87 exchange, electrochemical removal, membrane technology; Wang et al., 2018) affected
88 by significant disadvantages (e.g., incomplete removal, high-energy requirements and
89 production of toxic sludge), biosorption represents a highly cost-effective alternative for
90 the treatment of heavy metal-contaminated effluents, thanks to the low operational
91 costs, high efficiency and comparatively less sludge production (Kratochvil and
92 Volesky, 1998; Wang et al., 2018).

93 In this perspective, the present paper explores the recovery and valorization of EPS
94 from anammox granular waste sludge as biosorbent for the removal of some heavy

95 metals commonly found in wastewaters both of civil and industrial origins (lead,
96 copper, nickel, zinc). Batch equilibrium biosorption tests were carried out by treating
97 single- and multi-metal aqueous solutions with the recovered anammox EPS. The
98 anammox EPS sorption properties were then compared to those of pristine granules.
99 Biosorption mechanisms were investigated combining a series of spectroscopic
100 techniques.

101

102 2. Materials and Methods

103 2.1 EPS extraction/recovery from anammox granular waste sludge

104 EPS were extracted from anammox granular waste sludge originating from a full-scale
105 reactor in Rotterdam (Dokhaven-Sluisijesdijk WWTP, van der Star et al., 2007). The
106 pH-based chemical extraction method developed by Lotti et al. (2019a) was applied
107 with a modification: EPS were extracted from anammox granules under alkaline
108 conditions (0.1 M NaOH, pH 12) without acidic precipitation/recovery. The EPS
109 extracts were then dialyzed (3.5 kDa molecular weight cut-off, MWCO) against
110 ultrapure water (3 sequences of dialysis of about 8 hours each). This procedure yielded
111 EPS dispersions directly suitable for multi- and single-metal sorption studies. The
112 average EPS extraction yield was calculated based on the volatile solid content of the
113 starting biomass ($\text{mgTS}_{\text{EPS}}/\text{gVS}_{\text{granules}}$) according to the method described in
114 *Supplementary material* (Figure S1).

115 2.2 Anammox EPS and granule characterization

116 The Total Solids (TS, g) were measured by placing the extracted EPS/granules in oven
117 (105 °C) for about 24/48 h and then weighting the samples. The ash content (Ash, g)

118 was determined by putting the dried EPS/granules in muffle-furnace (550 °C) for 2 h
119 and then weighting the samples. The Volatile Solids (VS, g) were calculated as the
120 weight difference between TS and Ash. The measurements were carried out in triplicate
121 and the results (in terms of VS/TS ratio, g/g) are expressed as average values \pm standard
122 deviation. The granule particle size distribution was determined by an image analysis
123 procedure adapted from Tijhuis et al. (1994) and using the software Image ProPlus®.
124 Anammox EPS and granule samples were also analyzed in triplicate by a Varian 720-
125 ES Inductively Coupled Plasma - Atomic Emission Spectrometer (ICP-AES) equipped
126 with a pneumatic nebulizer and a cyclonic spray chamber to measure the metal
127 concentrations (in terms of mg/KgTS).

128 2.3 Heavy metal aqueous solutions

129 For single-metal sorption tests, synthetic aqueous solutions, each containing one of the
130 selected heavy metal ion M^{2+} (Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}), were prepared dissolving
131 $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $ZnCl_2$, respectively, in ultrapure water, with
132 concentrations ranging between 10 and 1000 mgM^{2+}/L (pH=4.41, 4.59, 4.51 and 4.44
133 for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} aqueous solutions, respectively, at 1000 mgM^{2+}/L). For
134 multi-metal sorption studies, a solution containing all the selected heavy metal ions
135 simultaneously was prepared dissolving $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $ZnCl_2$
136 in ultrapure water (80 gM^{2+}/L each, pH 5.25). $Pb(NO_3)_2$ (purity $\geq 99.0\%$), $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$
137 (purity $\geq 99.0\%$), $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (purity $\geq 99.9\%$) and $ZnCl_2$ (purity $\geq 98.0\%$) were
138 purchased by Sigma-Aldrich. For the preparation of all samples, ultrapure water was
139 used after filtration through a Milli-Q system (Millipore).

140 2.4 Heavy metal biosorption studies with anammox EPS

141 The biosorption properties of the extracted anammox EPS were assessed with
142 equilibrium single-metal biosorption tests at laboratory scale, by treating synthetic
143 aqueous solutions each containing one of the selected heavy metal ions M^{2+} . To
144 evaluate the effect of the initial heavy metal concentration (C_0 , mg/L) on biosorption,
145 heavy metal solutions (4 mL) with concentrations ranging between 10 and 1000
146 mgM^{2+}/L were mixed anammox EPS dispersions (4 mL, 12.95 ± 1.65 gTS_{EPS}/L) in
147 separate flasks and kept in contact under stirred conditions (120 rpm) at a temperature
148 of 20 ± 0.5 °C for 6 hours. Based on the information available in literature (Liu et al.,
149 2015; Wei et al., 2016; Sajjad et al., 2017) and on preliminary kinetic studies (Figure S2
150 in *Supplementary material*), a contact time of 6 hours was considered as sufficient to
151 attain sorption equilibrium. The pH of the mixed EPS-heavy metal aqueous systems was
152 adjusted to 5.0 (for Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+}) - 6.0 (for Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+}) by adding 0.1 M HCl and
153 NaOH aqueous solutions, in order to avoid precipitation of metal salts.

154 Multi-metal biosorption studies were performed under conditions similar to those
155 described for single-metal biosorption tests: an aqueous solution containing all the
156 selected heavy metal ions simultaneously (4 mL, 80 mgM^{2+}/L each) was mixed with an
157 anammox EPS dispersion (4 mL, 15.22 gTS_{EPS}/L), providing a contact time of 8 hours
158 under stirring (120 rpm) at a temperature of 20 ± 0.5 °C. Since the lower initial metal
159 concentrations, these tests were carried out at pH 6.0 (by adjusting the original pH of
160 the EPS-metal aqueous system with 0.1 M HCl/NaOH), avoiding metal precipitation.

161 Both in single- and multi-metal biosorption tests, the measure of the residual metal
162 concentrations at equilibrium (C_e , mg/L) was performed in triplicate by a Varian 720-
163 ES Inductively Coupled Plasma - Atomic Emission Spectrometer (ICP-AES), after

164 dialysis (3.5 kDa molecular weight cut-off) against ultrapure water. The removal
 165 efficiencies (%) and adsorption capacities (Q_e , mg/g) were calculated according to the
 166 following Eqs. (1) and (2), respectively:

$$167 \quad \text{Removal efficiency} = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \cdot 100 \quad (\%) \quad (1)$$

$$168 \quad Q_e = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{m} \cdot V \quad \left(\frac{mg}{g}\right) \quad (2)$$

169 where V (L) is the solution volume and m (g) is the sorbent mass. The experimental
 170 adsorption isotherm curves, describing the relationship between adsorption capacity
 171 (i.e., mass of solute adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent, Q_e , mg/g) and residual metal
 172 concentration (C_e , mg/L) at equilibrium, were therefore determined. Langmuir and
 173 Freundlich adsorption isotherm models (Eqs. 3 and 4, respectively) were applied to
 174 interpret the observed profiles:

$$175 \quad Q_e = \frac{b \cdot Q_m \cdot C_e}{1 + b \cdot C_e} \quad (3)$$

$$176 \quad Q_e = K_f \cdot C_e^{1/n} \quad (4)$$

177 where Q_m (mg/g) is the theoretical maximum adsorption capacity, b (L/mg) is the
 178 Langmuir constant related to adsorption energy, K_f (L/g) is the energy binding constant
 179 reflecting the affinity of the sorbent for the sorbate and n is the Freundlich constant. The
 180 equilibrium parameter R_L , a dimensionless constant related to the separation factor
 181 (Balarak et al., 2017), was inferred from the Langmuir equation and determined as
 182 follows (Eq. 5):

$$183 \quad R_L = \frac{1}{1 + b \cdot C_0^*} \quad (-) \quad (5)$$

184 where C_0^* (mg/L) is the highest tested initial metal concentration. The value of R_L
185 identifies the type of isotherm: irreversible ($R_L=0$), favorable ($0<R_L<1$), linear ($R_L=1$) or
186 unfavorable ($R_L>1$).

187 2.5 Heavy metal biosorption studies with anammox granules

188 The biosorption properties of the extracted anammox EPS were compared to those of
189 pristine granules.

190 Anammox granules were pre-treated to overcome their pH buffer capacity, which
191 produced a progressive alkalizing effect in the aqueous medium, due to variable mineral
192 and/or organic fractions present in the biomass: anammox granules were subjected to
193 consecutive washing cycles with 0.45 % (w/v) NaCl (aqueous solutions in
194 demineralized water, pH 5) until reaching a stable pH 5 in the liquid bulk. The
195 described pre-treatment method was time-consuming but also slightly invasive for the
196 biomass: lower pH values might speed up the desorption processes, but also
197 compromise the granular matrix and promote cell lysis phenomena. In addition, the use
198 of buffer solution (e.g., containing phosphate) could promote competitions with the
199 heavy metal cations to be adsorbed on the same binding sites. The pre-treated granules
200 were drained by using a metal sieve (200 μm pore size): their VS/TS ratio (g/g) was
201 determined and compared to that of the untreated biomass; the conversion factor
202 between granule wet weight (WW, g) and dry weight (TS, g) was also evaluated (i.e.,
203 WW/TS, g/g).

204 To determine the experimental adsorption isotherm curves, a series of each metal ion
205 solution with concentrations ranging between 5 and 500 mg/L were mixed with
206 anammox granules ($1.69 \pm 0.20 \text{ gTS}_{\text{granules/L}}$) in separate flasks at pH 5.0 (for Pb^{2+} and
207 Cu^{2+}) - 6.0 (for Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+}) and maintained under stirring (120 rpm) for 6 hours at a

208 temperature of 20 ± 0.5 °C. Each sample was then filtered through 0.45 μm filter paper
209 and analyzed by ICP-AES for the measurement of the residual heavy metal
210 concentrations at equilibrium (C_e , mg/L). The removal efficiencies (%) and adsorption
211 capacities (Q_e , mg/g) were calculated as previously described for the extracted EPS
212 (Eqs. 1 and 2, respectively); similarly, the equilibrium sorption data were correlated by
213 Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm models (Eqs. 3 and 4, respectively).

214 2.6 Biosorption mechanisms

215 Combining a series of spectroscopic techniques, a detailed description of the EPS/metal
216 interaction at the molecular level was provided, proposing a mechanistic hypothesis for
217 metal biosorption.

218 The occurrence of ion exchange mechanisms associated to the heavy metal adsorption
219 was assessed measuring the concentration of alkali and alkaline earth metal ions (e.g.,
220 Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} and Na^+) released in solution simultaneously with the heavy metal
221 uptake via ICP-AES.

222 Hydrodynamic diameter and Z-potential of EPS dispersions (0.01% w/v) in contact with
223 increasing concentrations of the selected heavy metal ions (0.001-1 mM) were detected
224 by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) at 90° and Phase Analysis Light Scattering,
225 respectively (90Plus PALS, Brookhaven Instruments Corporation, USA). EPS samples
226 treating highly concentrated heavy metal-contaminated aqueous solutions ($C_0=500$
227 mg/L) were also observed with a scanning electron microscope (SEM Zeiss Evo MA15;
228 sample coating with gold) and analyzed with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry
229 (EDS Oxford Inca 250) to determine their elemental compositions.

230 To address the main EPS functional groups acting as metal-binding sites, Fourier
231 Transform-Infrared (FT-IR) spectra of EPS samples before and after heavy metal

232 biosorption were obtained in the transmission mode using a BioRad FTS-40
233 spectrometer (4 cm⁻¹ resolution, 64 scans, spectral range 2000–400 cm⁻¹, DTGS
234 detector).

235

236 3. Results and Discussion

237 3.1 Anammox granule and EPS characterization

238 The particle size distribution of anammox granules is reported in Figure 1; the
239 characteristic diameters D10, D50 and D90 were 180.9, 317.0 and 871.2 μm,
240 respectively. The average VS/TS ratio of anammox granules was 0.909 ± 0.002 g/g,
241 while the granule wet weight on dry weight ratio was 11.54 ± 0.98 g/g. The EPS
242 alkaline extraction yielded an average amount of EPS of 355.24 ± 4.48
243 mgTS_{EPS}/gVS_{granules}, in agreement with that reported by Lotti et al. (2019a). The VS/TS
244 ratio of the extracted anammox EPS was 0.809 ± 0.020 g/g.

245 The tested granular sludge came from a full-scale reactor treating the reject water of a
246 waste activated sludge anaerobic digester; since sewage sludge retains large part of the
247 metal content entering the WWTP, the presence of alkali, alkaline earth and heavy
248 metals was detected both in anammox granules and extracted EPS (Table S1 in
249 *Supplementary material*). Some metals (e.g., Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn) are mostly present in the
250 EPS (i.e., adsorbed by granules via extracellular uptake) and do not solubilize in the
251 extraction process: considering an average EPS content in granules of about 36% (w/w),
252 metal concentrations (in terms of mg/kgTS_{EPS}) in the extracted EPS can increase up to
253 2.8 times with respect to pristine granules. Other metals are mainly present in the cells
254 (e.g., adsorbed by granules via intracellular accumulation and/or cell wall sorption)
255 and/or as metal precipitates within the granular biomass: their concentration in the

256 extracted EPS is therefore expected to be lower than in the original granules and
257 eventually close to zero; this might be the case of Al, Co, Cr, Mo, V, Pb.
258 The applied granule pre-treatment allowed overcoming the biomass pH buffer capacity:
259 a stable pH 5 was achieved in the aqueous medium via consecutive washing cycles of
260 granules with 0.45% w/v NaCl at pH 5 (at least 3 changes of the liquid bulk), ensuring a
261 total contact time (in 0.45% w/v NaCl, pH 5) in the range of 100-400 hours dependent
262 on the granule concentration (Figure S3 in *Supplementary material*). The pre-treatment
263 permitted to maintain constant pH conditions during the metal sorption tests, thus
264 avoiding uncontrolled formation of metal precipitates due to the increase of pH
265 observed in preliminary sorption studies using untreated granules (data not shown). The
266 alkalizing effect of the untreated granules under the conditions applied during the heavy
267 metal biosorption experiments (pH 5-6) was likely due to the dissolution of carbonate-
268 precipitates formed within the granular biomass during the operations in the parent full-
269 scale reactor (operational pH>7) (Lin et al., 2013). A meaningful variation of VS/TS
270 ratio was not detected after granule pre-treatment (VS/TS=0.888±0.007 g/g for pre-
271 treated granules).

272 3.2 Effect of initial metal concentration on heavy metal biosorption

273 The adsorption capacities (mg/g) and removal efficiencies (%) were determined as a
274 function of C_0 . Single-metal biosorption tests evidenced increasing heavy metal
275 adsorption capacities at equilibrium (Q_e , mg/g) as the initial metal concentration (C_0 ,
276 mg/L) increased, both for extracted EPS and granules (Figures 2a and 2b). C_0 provided
277 an important driving force to overcome the mass transfer resistances of the metal
278 between the aqueous and solid phase (Aksu et al., 2000), thus promoting adsorption
279 phenomena. At the same time, with increasing C_0 , the heavy metal ion competition for

280 the available binding sites increased (Zheng et al., 2008), thus reducing the percentage
281 removal efficiency (Figures 2c and 2d). The highest EPS adsorption capacities obtained
282 under the tested conditions were 84.9, 52.8, 21.7 and 7.4 mg/gTS_{EPS} for Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺
283 and Zn²⁺ respectively ($C_0=500$ mg/L). Free Pb²⁺ was found in the treated solution above
284 the detection limits of ICP-AES (in the order of $\mu\text{g/L}$) only for $C_0>40$ mg/L, thus
285 highlighting its large affinity towards EPS; a significant removal (about 93.9%) was
286 detected also for the highest tested concentration ($C_0=500$ mg/L). Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺
287 removals decreased from 90.8 and 60.9% to 62.2 and 28.3%, respectively, with
288 increasing C_0 from 5 to 500 mg/L; lower removal efficiencies were obtained for Zn²⁺
289 (15.9 and 10.2% for C_0 equal to 5 and 500 mg/L, respectively). Concerning anammox
290 granules, the highest observed metal uptakes at equilibrium were 103.7, 36.1, 48.2 and
291 49.8 mg/gTS_{granules} for Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ respectively ($C_0=500$ mg/L). At the
292 lowest C_0 of 5 mg/L, anammox granules were able to remove most of the metal content
293 of the treated solutions (98.5, 97.4, 98.6 and 95.1% of Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺,
294 respectively), while the removal efficiencies appeared significantly decreased for the
295 highest C_0 of 500 mg/L (33.5, 12.6, 15.5 and 14.2% for Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺,
296 respectively), consistently with the results obtained for the recovered EPS.

297 3.3 Comparison between anammox granules and extracted EPS

298 Both anammox granules and extracted EPS exhibited metal-binding capacities
299 equivalent or higher than other conventional and/or unconventional sorbent media
300 (Table S2 in *Supplementary material*). However, different sorption pathways were
301 detected comparing their ability in removing metal cations from contaminated aqueous
302 systems. Describing granules as dense microbial aggregates, comprising metabolically
303 active microbial cells embedded in an EPS matrix (Liu and Tay, 2004), it is expected

304 that the extracellular uptake plays a crucial role in metal biosorption phenomena.
305 Indeed, EPS are rich in ionizable functional groups (e.g., carboxyl and hydroxyl groups)
306 able to interact with cationic species in solution, thus representing potential metal-
307 binding sites. Heavy metal uptakes in the same order of magnitude of other granular
308 biomasses (i.e., aerobic, anaerobic granules) were observed (Table S3 in *Supplementary*
309 *material*): this would suggest that metal biosorption is more dependent on the three-
310 dimensional porous structure of the sorbent (and therefore on the spatial configuration
311 of EPS polymeric chains and corresponding availability of binding sites) rather than the
312 quality of EPS. In other words, given the similar biosorption figures for different
313 granular sludges, biosorption does not seem to be dependent on the specific nature of
314 the sludge/EPS considered, but rather connected to structural aspects of the granules.
315 Hypothesising that all the active metal-binding sites of anammox granules are localized
316 on the EPS matrix, greater metal sorption capacities would be expected for the extracted
317 EPS compared to pristine granules (up to 2.8 times higher in terms of $\text{mgM}^{2+}/\text{gTS}$,
318 considering an average EPS content of about 36% w/w). However, other mechanisms
319 might participate in the heavy metal sorption promoted by anammox granules: cell wall
320 adsorption and intracellular accumulation are usually common ways for biosorption
321 (Vijayaraghavan et al., 2008). This could especially explain the lower zinc uptake
322 observed for the extracted EPS compared to pristine biomass: zinc is an essential co-
323 factor for a large number of proteins, assolving to many structural and/or catalitic
324 functions and, as obseved by Limcharoensuk et al. (2015), bacteria are able to rapidly
325 accumulate it on their cell walls.
326 Besides the potential contribution in metal adsorption exerted by other components than
327 EPS, it should be highlighted that the availability of binding sites of EPS themselves

328 could be altered by the chemical extraction method applied. Some reports have shown
329 that EPS extracted with chemical methods display meaningful differences in their
330 ability to bind heavy metal ions, likely due to contamination of the recovered EPS with
331 the chemicals used during the extraction (d'Abzac et al., 2010). The chemical extraction
332 protocol here applied is based on the use of 0.1 M NaOH as alkaline agent to solubilize
333 the EPS matrix. Although the extraction protocol includes dialysis (3.5 kDa MWCO),
334 the EPS extracts showed a relatively high content of Na⁺ ions (11.6 mg/gTS_{EPS}, Table
335 S1 in *Supplementary material*), which could compete with the heavy metal ions to be
336 adsorbed on the available binding sites. The extraction under alkaline conditions might
337 also affect the conformation of EPS components through the loss of protein tertiary
338 and/or quaternary structure. This can promote specific interactions among proteins,
339 resulting in more significant entanglement and progressive folding (i.e., association) of
340 the peptidic chains, with subsequent reduction of the specific surface area and binding
341 site availability.

342 Moreover, structural aspects of the sorbent medium can affect the performance in
343 removing metal cations. While the highly porous structure of granules, with abundant
344 and accessible sorption sites, promote the sequestration of contaminants upon diffusion
345 into their deeper layers and channels (Liu et al., 2003), the use of EPS extracts in a sol-
346 like state could result in weaker solute-sorbent interactions (or not strong enough to
347 overcome the forces extended by the solvent).

348 3.4 Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm models

349 The interpretation of the equilibrium biosorption data via Langmuir and Freundlich
350 adsorption isotherm models confirmed some differences in the sorption pathways
351 followed by anammox EPS and granules. Figure 3 shows the experimental sorption

352 isotherm curves and the related fits via Langmuir and Freundlich models. Based on the
353 model statistical indicators (Table S4 in *Supplementary material*), using anammox
354 granules as biosorbent medium, a Zn^{2+} mono-layer biosorption was predicted due to the
355 better statistical fitting via Langmuir model; Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} biosorption data were
356 better simulated by Freundlich model, thus suggesting a multi-layer biosorption on a
357 heterogeneous surface. Using the EPS extracts as biosorbent medium, a Pb^{2+} multi-layer
358 biosorption was predicted because of the better statistical fitting via Freundlich model;
359 Langmuir model was more representative of Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} equilibrium biosorption
360 data, thus implying an uniform and mono-layer adsorption on the EPS surface: the EPS-
361 Cu^{2+}/Zn^{2+} interactions could be not strong enough to overcome the forces extended by
362 the solvent except in the first layer, being both solute and sorbent in a sol-like state. The
363 slight differences in R^2 values observed for Ni^{2+} adsorption by anammox EPS, reflecting
364 the simultaneously applicability of both theoretical models, suggested as mono- or
365 multi-layer attachment, possibly with chemical interactions between EPS and metal
366 ions, and also between the sorbates molecules, could explain the biosorption phenomena
367 (Wang et al., 2018). Further information can be deduced from the model parameters
368 (Table S4 in *Supplementary material*). The $0 < 1/n < 1$ values in Freundlich model (0.422-
369 0.680 and 0.227-0.336 for extracted EPS and anammox granules, respectively) implied
370 a favorable metal biosorption by anammox EPS and granules (Wang et al., 2018),
371 consistent with the $0 < R_L < 1$ values (0.005-0.369 and 0.004-0.280 for extracted EPS and
372 anammox granules, respectively) in Langmuir model. Similarly to the Langmuir
373 constant b , the values of the energy binding constant K_f in Freundlich model reflected
374 the metal binding affinity of the sorbent in the following orders: $Pb^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$
375 for extracted EPS and $Pb^{2+} > Cu^{2+} \sim Ni^{2+} \sim Zn^{2+}$ for anammox granules.

376 3.5 Multi-metal biosorption studies

377 Similar metal-binding capacities were observed for the extracted EPS in multi- and
378 single-metal biosorption experiments (Table 1): significant competitions among
379 different heavy metal ions for the available EPS binding sites were ruled out. Moreover,
380 the total heavy metal uptake in the case of multi-metal systems (14.81 mg/gTS_{EPS}) was
381 higher than the amount of each metal ion adsorbed in single-metal sorption tests,
382 indicating the capability of EPS in adsorbing multi-metal ions. Similar evidences were
383 found by Sun et al. (2009) for Zn²⁺ and Co²⁺ binary sorption on EPS from aerobic
384 granules, thus supporting the consistency of these considerations, regardless of the
385 quality of EPS and original microbial aggregate. Many conventional techniques for the
386 heavy metal removal (e.g., ion exchange resins, nanofiltration membranes) are often
387 designed to target one contaminant at a time, thus making their use impractical for
388 environmentally polluted waters and/or wastewaters where several contaminants occur
389 simultaneously (Bolisetty et al., 2019). Conversely, the sorption capability of extracted
390 anammox EPS in multi-metal aqueous systems might be exploited in technologies for
391 the treatment of effluents contaminated by several heavy metals.

392 3.6 Biosorption mechanisms

393 The process scale-up should be supported by a deeper molecular-level understanding of
394 the biosorption processes, made challenging by the complexity of the mechanisms
395 involved. This is hampered by the fact that the fine physic-chemical characterization of
396 EPS recovered from biofilm-based engineered systems is still far from complete
397 (Seviour et al., 2019). The investigation should start with the surface properties of the
398 sorbent, representing a key element in all adsorption phenomena. The removal
399 efficiencies of contaminants are strongly dependent on both their species and sorbent

400 surface charge through mechanisms of electrostatic attraction. Modifications of the
401 surface properties of the sorbent could be promoted by the pH of the medium, that not
402 only affects the speciation of the solutes, but can also change the surface charge of the
403 sorbent via protonation or deprotonation (Wang et al., 2018). The effect of pH on the Z-
404 potential of aqueous solutions containing EPS extracted from anammox granular sludge
405 was recently reported in the literature (Lotti et al., 2019a). In brief, at $\text{pH} \leq 4$, EPS
406 surface is largely protonated and Z-potential is close to neutrality $|Z_{\text{pot}}| \leq 10 \text{ mV}$: more
407 H^+ are available in solution to protonate the active sites on the EPS surface and compete
408 with the heavy metal ions to be adsorbed. For higher values of pH, deprotonation occurs
409 and the EPS surface becomes negatively charged, thus increasing the ability to interact
410 with positively charged metals. In the tested sorption conditions (pH 5-6), anammox
411 EPS were negatively charged ($Z_{\text{pot}} \leq -20 \text{ mV}$, Lotti et al., 2019a) and could attract metal
412 cations via electrostatic interactions as first step of biosorption, thus providing more
413 opportunities for further polymer-metal interactions (Wang et al., 2018). The prediction
414 on how biosorption proceeds is difficult: physic-chemical interactions between heavy
415 metal cations and EPS (anionic) functional groups, based on ion exchange, surface
416 complexation, redox reaction and micro-deposition, might be involved, individually or
417 in combination (Wang et al., 2018). FI-IR spectroscopy evidenced that anammox EPS
418 were rich in potential metal-binding sites (e.g., amine and carboxyl groups), disclosing a
419 role of protein- and polysaccharide-like substances in the heavy metal uptake (i.e.,
420 significant shifts of the corresponding peaks were detected in the FT-IR spectra of EPS
421 samples after heavy metal sorption, as described more detailed in Figure S4 in
422 *Supplementary material*). In agreement with the literature, reporting the ion exchange as
423 a common mechanism to describe the metal biosorption by EPS (Li and Yu, 2014)

424 and/or biomass (Sajjad et al., 2017), the heavy metal uptake by anammox EPS and
425 granules was associated to releases of alkali and alkaline earth metal ions (e.g., Ca^{2+} ,
426 Na^+ , Mg^{2+} and K^+) into the liquid bulk, resulting from a relatively lower affinity and
427 competitiveness of the exchangeable cations to bind with the sorbent (Wang et al.,
428 2010). Figure 4 compares the amounts of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} adsorbed by
429 anammox EPS and granules with those of Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} and Na^+ found in the aqueous
430 medium after the heavy metal sorption tests ($C_0=500$ mg/L). It was noticed that the
431 heavy metal adsorption by anammox EPS was mainly associated to Ca^{2+} and Na^+
432 releases in solution, which accounted for 93.5, 93.4, 88.3 and 95.6% of the total amount
433 of metal ions discarded by EPS following the Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} adsorption,
434 respectively, with a lower release of K^+ and Mg^{2+} also detected. Ion-exchange
435 mechanisms were also observed for the pristine granules: Ca^+ represented less than 1%
436 of the total release following adsorption, while Na^+ ions were the most abundant (93.1,
437 94.2, 75.2 and 92.4% of the total metal ion release for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}
438 biosorption, respectively), with a lower amount of K^+ (5.7, 5.8, 24.1 and 6.7% of the
439 total metal ion release for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} biosorption, respectively) detected
440 in the aqueous medium after biosorption. A non-stoichiometric exchange (i.e.,
441 release/adsorption ratios < 1 meq/meq) was observed both for anammox EPS and
442 pristine granules, suggesting that this process was not the only mechanism at play in
443 biosorption. In addition to ion exchange, complexation and surface precipitation are
444 considered as two of the major mechanisms responsible for the heavy metal-
445 EPS/biomass interaction (Li and Yu, 2014). Depending on metal speciation in response
446 to pH, directly affecting the metal solubility, many heavy metals can be also easily
447 precipitated into EPS/biomass or onto the surface of some mineral fraction contained in

448 EPS/biomass (Guibaud et al, 2009), thus greatly complicating the understanding of
449 sorption processes. In particular, for $C_0=500$ mg/L, ion exchange accounted for 46.4,
450 22.4, 26.1 and 32.6% of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} biosorption, respectively, by
451 anammox EPS and 88.6, 99.1 and 76.1% of the Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} uptake,
452 respectively, by anammox granules (data related to Pb^{2+} sorption are not clear, due to
453 the release/sorption ratios > 1 meq/meq).

454 It should be highlighted that the ion exchange contribution to heavy metal biosorption
455 by anammox EPS increased by 45, 110, 157 and 88%, for of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ,
456 respectively, decreasing C_0 from 500 to 200 mg/L. This evidence suggested a complex
457 interplay of other adsorption mechanisms more active for the highest initial metal
458 concentrations. Indeed, in single-metal biosorption tests at $C_0=500$ mg/L, polymer-
459 metal aqueous systems containing nickel and zinc appeared slightly unstable (potential
460 formation of micro – and/or nano-precipitates, not visually detectable), while lead and
461 copper co-precipitated with EPS as composite aggregates (aggregate size in the order of
462 mm, i.e., clearly visible). The Pb/Cu-EPS co-precipitates were observed with a scanning
463 electron microscope (SEM) for the surface morphology investigation: the surface
464 roughness indicated the presence of polymeric components, while regular crystalline
465 structures expected for metal precipitates were not appreciated (Figures S5a, S5b, S6a,
466 and S6b in *Supplementary material*). Considering the molecular composition of
467 anammox EPS reported in literature (i.e., $C_1H_{1.629}O_{0.503}N_{0.209}P_{0.009}$, 24.97 g $V_{EPS}/C-$
468 mol $_{EPS}$, Lotti et al., 2019a), metal/EPS weight and atomic ratios of the composite
469 aggregates were calculated based on the elemental analysis obtained via energy X-ray
470 dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) (Table 2). Details on the EDS analysis are reported in
471 *Supplementary material* (Figures S5c and S6c). The EPS presence in the aggregates was

472 confirmed by the O/C atomic ratios in agreement with those reported for pristine
473 anammox EPS (Lotti et al., 2019a). As emerged from EDS analysis, carbon, oxygen,
474 and heavy metals (i.e., Pb and Cu, respectively) were prevalent (in terms of atomic%
475 and weight%) in the aggregate composition, with weight and atomic ratios consistent
476 with the polymer-heavy metal co-precipitation. The EPS-heavy metal co-precipitation
477 phenomena observed in biosorption tests treating highly concentrated heavy metal-
478 contaminated aqueous solutions was probably not due to pH and/or ionic strength of the
479 aqueous systems: the experiments were designed selecting operative conditions that
480 avoided the precipitation of metal salts. The effect of ionic strength was not investigated
481 in this study, but the applied experimental conditions (Table S5 in *Supplementary*
482 *material*) would have allowed to overcome the competition with electrolyte cations,
483 thus promoting the metal adsorption processes. More likely, increasing the amount of
484 heavy metal ions adsorbed on the EPS binding sites, multiple-bridging complexation
485 phenomena might be promoted. In line with this hypothesis, divalent cations M^{2+} could
486 act as bridges for different EPS units. This would result in a strong increase of EPS
487 particle size, and in a reduction of the repulsive force among EPS units, thus leading to
488 aggregation and finally to precipitation, as also suggested by preliminary Zeta-potential
489 and Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) measurements (Figure S7 in *Supplementary*
490 *material*). Regardless of the mechanistic hypothesis, these findings would suggest that
491 anammox EPS might be applied as flocculant/complexing agent to pre-treat very
492 concentrated heavy metal-contaminated wastewaters: EPS would concentrate heavy
493 metals in the form of composite aggregates (i.e., metal concentration in the polymer-
494 metal aggregates higher than those adsorbed by EPS in a sol-like state), easily separable

495 from the clarified effluent via sedimentation or filtration, thus greatly simplifying the
496 post-treatment separation phase.

497 3.7 Outlook and perspectives

498 Anammox granular waste sludge might be easily valorized as high-performance and
499 cost-effective biosorbent medium for the treatment of heavy metal-contaminated
500 effluents. If compared to conventional suspended microbial flocs, granular biomasses
501 feature the advantages of compact structure and superior settleability, which can
502 facilitate the post-separation (Adav et al., 2009) in water and/or wastewater treatment
503 systems. Although the specific surface area of granules is generally lower than activated
504 sludge (Zheng et al., 2005), granules are highly porous and contain abundant and
505 accessible adsorption sites in the interior, which enables them to trap various
506 contaminants upon diffusion into their deeper layers and channels (Liu et al., 2003).
507 A potential process scale-up concerning the anammox EPS recovery/valorization as
508 metal biosorbent in WWTPs requires further investigations. First, a deeper
509 understanding of the polymer modification due to the extraction would lead to an
510 optimization of the extraction protocol as a function of the properties required for the
511 recovered EPS. Then, further improvements of technological aspects (e.g., devolving
512 EPS-based sorbent media with the involvement of waste-based carrier materials and/or
513 composite hydrogels) would enhance the EPS sorption properties. Based on the results
514 described above, an interesting route to engineer the metal-binding ability of anammox
515 EPS might be the application of EPS-based flocculant/complexing agent to pre-treat
516 very concentrated heavy metal-contaminated effluents (e.g., galvanic and mining
517 wastewaters). Conceiving the treatment unit in this way, technological limitations due to
518 the use of EPS in a sol-like state would be avoided, in addition to the advantage in using

519 a bio-based commodity of renewable origin in substitution to chemical agents usually
520 applied in these types of process. In the case of effluents contaminated by a single heavy
521 metal (condition that can be relevant for many kinds of industrial wastewaters, Bolisetty
522 and Mezzenga, 2016), the use of anammox EPS as flocculant/biosorbent media might
523 also provide heavy metal recovery strategies. Indeed, amyloid fibrils, also detected in
524 anammox EPS (Lotti et al., 2019b), are able to reduce metal ions into metal
525 nanoparticles via a bio-mineralization processes, thus enabling the recovery of
526 expensive heavy metal ions (Bolisetty et al., 2011; Bolisetty and Mezzenga, 2016).
527 Hypothesizing the same ability for anammox EPS and providing a phase of heavy metal
528 recovery in designing the treatment unit, metal content in the sludge derived from the
529 treatment of heavy metal-contaminated effluents might be greatly reduced, thus helping
530 its treatment/disposal.

531 In compliance with the restrictive environmental legislation concerning the heavy metal
532 pollution, the potential application fields of anammox EPS/granular waste sludge as
533 metal biosorbent media might be multiple. They could be applied to treat heavy metal-
534 rich industrial effluents, but also to pre-treat municipal wastewater before biological
535 processes, thus avoiding metal accumulation into the secondary sludge, that could
536 compromise its valorization in agriculture. Considering the EPS recovery potentials in
537 full-scale anammox granular sludge installations reported by Lotti et al. (2019a) (about
538 40 g EPS per kgNH₄⁺-N removed from wastewater by anammox process, using an
539 alkaline extraction) and the maximum adsorption capacities obtained in this study,
540 significant metal removal potentials can be speculated: 3.57, 2.22, 0.91 and 0.31
541 gM²⁺/kgNH₄⁺-N for Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺, respectively. These values would allow

542 to design technologies able to target large part of the metal content entering the
543 treatment unit, especially as concerns lead and copper.
544 The application in full-scale WWTPs would also require an in-depth analysis
545 demonstrating its technical-economic feasibility: in view of the EPS extraction costs,
546 which will have to be carefully evaluated, the system might have a positive economic
547 balance since the raw material consists of a waste product, with high costs of
548 handling/disposal, and the extraction phase makes use of inexpensive chemicals (e.g.,
549 alkaline/acidic solutions). EPS-based biosorbent media might be produced and applied
550 *in situ* or destined to other WWTPs and/or industrial sectors, originating a bio-based
551 commodity with economic streams and markets.

552 Regardless of the metal biosorption performance, the extraction of EPS from anammox
553 granular sludge could be also interpreted as a waste sludge pre-treatment. As suggested
554 by Lotti et al. (2019a), the combination of EPS extraction with the conventional excess
555 sludge treatment processes (i.e., anaerobic/aerobic digestion) could allow not only to
556 recover a valuable commodity from a waste product, but also to improve the sludge
557 treatment efficiency thanks to the sludge volume/mass reduction and enhanced
558 digestibility and dewaterability of the remaining (i.e., non-extracted) sludge due to the
559 alkaline treatment involved in the EPS extraction protocol: these considerations should
560 be experimentally evaluated.

561

562 4. Conclusions

563 Both anammox granules and extracted EPS featured high metal-binding capacities
564 (84.9, 52.8, 21.7 and 7.4 mg/gTS_{EPS} and 103.7, 36.1, 48.2 and 49.8 mg/gTS_{granules} for
565 Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺, respectively, in single-metal biosorption tests at $C_0=500$

566 mg/L), suggesting their potential valorization for the treatment of heavy metal-
567 contaminated wastewaters, according to a circular economy approach in waste sludge
568 management. Comparing pristine granules and extracted EPS for their ability in
569 removing heavy metals from contaminated aqueous systems, different biosorption
570 pathways were detected: besides the potential metal uptake exerted by other
571 components than EPS in pristine granules, modifications of polymer chain entanglement
572 and functional group availability due to the alkaline extraction might alter the metal-
573 binding ability of the extracted EPS. The capability of anammox EPS in binding heavy
574 metal ions from multi-metal aqueous systems indicated their suitability for the treatment
575 of effluents contaminated by several heavy metals. A molecular-level analysis,
576 supported by a complete set of spectroscopic techniques, disclosed a multifaceted
577 adsorption mechanism, involving a combination of electrostatic interaction, ion-
578 exchange, complexation, and precipitation.

579

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588

589 References

- 590 Adav, S.S., Lee, D.J., Lai, J.Y., 2009. Treating chemical industries influent using
591 aerobic granular sludge: Recent development. *J. Taiwan Inst. Chem. Eng.* 40, 333–336.
592 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2009.02.002>
- 593 Aksu, Z., Akpınar, D., 2000. Modelling of simultaneous biosorption of phenol and
594 nickel(II) onto dried aerobic activated sludge. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 21, 87–99.
595 [https://doi.org/10.1016/A1383-5866\(00\)00194-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/A1383-5866(00)00194-5)
- 596 Balarak, D., Mostafapour, F., Azarpira, H., Joghataei, A., 2017. Langmuir, Freundlich,
597 Temkin and Dubinin–radushkevich Isotherms Studies of Equilibrium Sorption of
598 Ampicilin onto Montmorillonite Nanoparticles. *J. Pharm. Res. Int.* 20, 1–9.
599 <https://doi.org/10.9734/jpri/2017/38056>
- 600 Bolisetty, S., Mezzenga, R., 2016. Amyloid-carbon hybrid membranes for universal
601 water purification. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 11, 365–371.
602 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2015.310>
- 603 Bolisetty, S., Peydayesh, M., Mezzenga, R., 2019. Sustainable technologies for water
604 purification from heavy metals: review and analysis. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 48, 463–487.
605 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8cs00493e>
- 606 Bolisetty, S., Vallooran, J.J., Adamcik, J., Handschin, S., Gramm, F., Mezzenga, R.,
607 2011. Amyloid-mediated synthesis of giant, fluorescent, gold single crystals and their
608 hybrid sandwiched composites driven by liquid crystalline interactions. *J. Colloid
609 Interface Sci.* 361, 90–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2011.05.018>
- 610 Cantinho, P., Matos, M., Trancoso, M.A., dos Santos, M.M.C., 2016. Behaviour and
611 fate of metals in urban wastewater treatment plants: a review. *Int. J. Environ. Sci.
612 Technol.* 13, 359–386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/A13762-015-0887-x>

613 d'Abzac, P., Bordas, F., van Hullebusch, E., Lens, P.N.L., Guibaud, G., 2010. Effects of
614 extraction procedures on metal binding properties of extracellular polymeric substances
615 (EPS) from anaerobic granular sludges. *Colloids Surfaces B Biointerfaces* 80, 161–168.
616 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfb.2010.05.043>

617 Feng, C., Lotti, T., Canziani, R., Lin, Y., Tagliabue, C., Malpei, F., 2020. Extracellular
618 biopolymers recovered as raw biomaterials from waste granular sludge and potential
619 applications: A critical review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 753, 142051.
620 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142051>

621 Flemming, H.C., Neu, T.R., Wozniak, D.J., 2007. The EPS matrix: The “House of
622 Biofilm Cells.” *J. Bacteriol.* 189, 7945–7947. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JB.00858-07>

623 Flemming, H.C., Wingender, J., 2010. The biofilm matrix. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 8, 623–
624 633. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro2415>

625 Flemming, H.C., Wingender, J., Szewzyk, U., Steinberg, P., Rice, S.A., Kjelleberg, S.,
626 2016. Biofilms: An emergent form of bacterial life. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 14, 563–575.
627 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro.2016.94>

628 Guibaud, G., Bhatia, D., d'Abzac, P., Bourven, I., Bordas, F., van Hullebusch, E.D.,
629 Lens, P.N.L., 2012. Cd(II) and Pb(II) sorption by extracellular polymeric substances
630 (EPS) extracted from anaerobic granular biofilms: Evidence of a pH sorption-edge. *J.*
631 *Taiwan Inst. Chem. Eng.* 43, 444–449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2011.12.007>

632 Guibaud, G., van Hullebusch, E., Bordas, F., d'Abzac, P., Joussein, E., 2009. Sorption
633 of Cd(II) and Pb(II) by exopolymeric substances (EPS) extracted from activated sludges
634 and pure bacterial strains: Modeling of the metal/ligand ratio effect and role of the
635 mineral fraction. *Bioresour. Technol.* 100, 2959–2968.
636 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2009.01.040>

637 Hargreaves, A.J., Vale, P., Whelan, J., Alibardi, L., Constantino, C., Dotro, G.,
638 Cartmell, E., Campo, P., 2018. Impacts of coagulation-flocculation treatment on the size
639 distribution and bioavailability of trace metals (Cu, Pb, Ni, Zn) in municipal
640 wastewater. *Water Res.* 128, 120–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.10.050>
641 He, J., Chen, J.P., 2014. A comprehensive review on biosorption of heavy metals by
642 algal biomass: Materials, performances, chemistry, and modeling simulation tools.
643 *Bioresour. Technol.* 160, 67–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2014.01.068>
644 Hu, Z., Lotti, T., de Kreuk, M., Kleerebezem, R., van Loosdrecht, M., Kruit, J., Jetten,
645 M.S.M., Kartal, B., 2013. Nitrogen removal by a nitrification-anammox bioreactor at low
646 temperature. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 79, 2807–2812.
647 <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.03987-12>
648 Kratochvil, D., Volesky, B., 1998. Advances in the biosorption of heavy metals. *Trends*
649 *Biotechnol.* 16, 291–300. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-7799\(98\)01218-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-7799(98)01218-9)
650 Lackner, S., Gilbert, E.M., Vlaeminck, S.E., Joss, A., Horn, H., van Loosdrecht,
651 M.C.M., 2014. Full-scale partial nitrification/anammox experiences - An application
652 survey. *Water Res.* 55, 292–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2014.02.032>
653 Li, N., Wei, D., Wang, S., Hu, L., Xu, W., Du, B., Wei, Q., 2017. Comparative study of
654 the role of extracellular polymeric substances in biosorption of Ni(II) onto
655 aerobic/anaerobic granular sludge. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 490, 754–761.
656 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2016.12.006>
657 Li, W.W., Yu, H.Q., 2014. Insight into the roles of microbial extracellular polymer
658 substances in metal biosorption. *Bioresour. Technol.* 160, 15–23.
659 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2013.11.074>
660 Limcharoensuk, T., Sooksawat, N., Sumarnrote, A., Awutpet, T., Kruatrachue, M.,

661 Pokethitiyook, P., Auesukaree, C., 2015. Bioaccumulation and biosorption of Cd²⁺ and
662 Zn²⁺ by bacteria isolated from a zinc mine in Thailand. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 122,
663 322–330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2015.08.013>

664 Lin, Y.M., Lotti, T., Sharma, P.K., van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., 2013. Apatite
665 accumulation enhances the mechanical property of anammox granules. *Water Research*
666 47(13), pp. 4556-4566. DOI: 10.1016/j.watres.2013.04.061

667 Lin, Y.M., Nierop, K.G.J., Girbal-Neuhauser, E., Adriaanse, M., van Loosdrecht,
668 M.C.M., 2015. Sustainable polysaccharide-based biomaterial recovered from waste
669 aerobic granular sludge as a surface coating material. *Sustain. Mater. Technol.* 4, 24–29.
670 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susmat.2015.06.002>

671 Lin, Y.M., Reino, C., Carrera, J., Pérez, J., van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., 2018.
672 Glycosylated amyloid-like proteins in the structural extracellular polymers of aerobic
673 granular sludge enriched with ammonium-oxidizing bacteria. *Microbiologyopen* 7, 1–
674 13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mbo3.616>

675 Liu, W., Zhang, J., Jin, Y., Zhao, X., Cai, Z., 2015. Adsorption of Pb(II), Cd(II) and
676 Zn(II) by extracellular polymeric substances extracted from aerobic granular sludge:
677 Efficiency of protein. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 3, 1223–1232.
678 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2015.04.009>

679 Liu, Y., Tay, J.H., 2004. State of the art of biogranulation technology for wastewater
680 treatment. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 22, 533–563.
681 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2004.05.001>

682 Liu, Y., Yang, S.F., Xu, H., Woon, K.H., Lin, Y.M., Tay, J.H., 2003. Biosorption
683 kinetics of cadmium(II) on aerobic granular sludge. *Process Biochem.* 38, 997–1001.
684 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-9592\(02\)00225-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-9592(02)00225-X)

685 Lotti, T., Carretti, E., Berti, D., Martina, M.R., Lubello, C., Malpei, F., 2019a.
686 Extraction, recovery and characterization of structural extracellular polymeric
687 substances from anammox granular sludge. *J. Environ. Manage.* 236, 649–656.
688 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.01.054>

689 Lotti, T., Carretti, E., Berti, D., Montis, C., Del Buffa, S., Lubello, C., Feng, C., Malpei,
690 F., 2019b. Hydrogels formed by anammox extracellular polymeric substances:
691 Structural and mechanical insights. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 1–9. [https://doi.org/10.1038/A41598-](https://doi.org/10.1038/A41598-019-47987-8)
692 [019-47987-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/A41598-019-47987-8)

693 Sajjad, M., Aziz, A., Kim, K.S., 2017. Biosorption and Binding Mechanisms of Ni²⁺
694 and Cd²⁺ with Aerobic Granules Cultivated in Different Synthetic Media. *Chem. Eng.*
695 *Technol.* 40, 2179–2187. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.201600419>

696 Scarlat, N., Dallemand, J.F., Fahl, F., 2018. Biogas: Developments and perspectives in
697 Europe. *Renew. Energy* 129, 457–472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.03.006>

698 Seviour, T., Derlon, N., Dueholm, M.S., Flemming, H.C., Girbal-Neuhauser, E., Horn,
699 H., Kjelleberg, S., van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., Lotti, T., Malpei, M.F., Nerenberg, R.,
700 Neu, T.R., Paul, E., Yu, H., Lin, Y., 2019. Extracellular polymeric substances of
701 biofilms: Suffering from an identity crisis. *Water Res.* 151, 1–7.
702 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.11.020>

703 Seviour, T., Yuan, Z., van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., Lin, Y., 2012. Aerobic sludge
704 granulation: A tale of two polysaccharides? *Water Res.* 46, 4803–4813.
705 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2012.06.018>

706 Sun, X.F., Wang, S.G., Zhang, X.M., Paul Chen, J., Li, X.M., Gao, B.Y., Ma, Y., 2009.
707 Spectroscopic study of Zn²⁺ and Co²⁺ binding to extracellular polymeric substances
708 (EPS) from aerobic granules. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 335, 11–17.

709 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2009.03.088>

710 Taglialegna, A., Lasa, I., Valle, J., 2017. Amyloid structures as biofilm matrix scaffolds.
711 *J. Bacteriol.* 198, 2579–2588. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JB.00122-16>

712 Tjihuis, L., Van Benthum, W.A.J., Van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., Heijnen, J.J., 1994. Solids
713 retention time in spherical biofilms in a biofilm airlift suspension reactor. *Biotech. and*
714 *bioeng.*, 44(8), 867-879. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.260440802>

715 van der Star, W.R.L., Abma, W.R., Blommers, D., Mulder, J.W., Tokutomi, T., Strous,
716 M., Picioreanu, C., van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., 2007. Startup of reactors for anoxic
717 ammonium oxidation: Experiences from the first full-scale anammox reactor in
718 Rotterdam. *Water Res.* 41, 4149–4163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2007.03.044>

719 Vijayaraghavan, K., Yun, Y.S., 2008. Bacterial biosorbents and biosorption. *Biotechnol.*
720 *Adv.* 26, 266–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2008.02.002>

721 Wang, B. Bin, Liu, X.T., Chen, J.M., Peng, D.C., He, F., 2018. Composition and
722 functional group characterization of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) in
723 activated sludge: the impacts of polymerization degree of proteinaceous substrates.
724 *Water Res.* 129, 133–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.11.008>

725 Wang, X.H., Song, R.H., Teng, S.X., Gao, M.M., Ni, J.Y., Liu, F.F., Wang, S.G., Gao,
726 B.Y., 2010. Characteristics and mechanisms of Cu(II) biosorption by disintegrated
727 aerobic granules. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 179, 431–437.
728 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2010.03.022>

729 Wei, D., Li, M., Wang, X., Han, F., Li, L., Guo, J., Ai, L., Fang, L., Liu, L., Du, B.,
730 Wei, Q., 2016. Extracellular polymeric substances for Zn(II) binding during its sorption
731 process onto aerobic granular sludge. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 301, 407–415.
732 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2015.09.018>

733 Wei, L., Li, J., Xue, M., Wang, S., Li, Q., Qin, K., Jiang, J., Ding, J., Zhao, Q., 2019.
734 Adsorption behaviors of Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ onto proteins, humic acid, and
735 polysaccharides extracted from sludge EPS: Sorption properties and mechanisms.
736 *Bioresour. Technol.* 291, 121868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.121868>
737 Zheng, Y., Fang, X., Ye, Z., Li, Y., Cai, W., 2008. Biosorption of Cu(II) on
738 extracellular polymers from *Bacillus* sp. F19. *J. Environ. Sci.* 20, 1288–1293.
739 [https://doi.org/10.1016/A1001-0742\(08\)62223-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/A1001-0742(08)62223-8)
740 Zheng, Y.M., Yu, H.Q., Sheng, G.P., 2005. Physical and chemical characteristics of
741 granular activated sludge from a sequencing batch airlift reactor. *Process Biochem.* 40,
742 645–650. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2004.01.056>
743

744 Figure captions

745

746 **Figure 1** - Particle size distribution of anammox granules.

747

748 **Figure 2** – Adsorption capacities (Q_e , mg/g) and removal efficiencies (%) observed for
749 anammox EPS (**a**, **c**, respectively) and pristine granules (**b**, **d**, respectively) towards the
750 selected heavy metal ions (Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) at increasing initial heavy metal
751 concentrations ($C_0=5\text{-}500$ mg/L). Adsorption capacities (Q_e , mg/g) are related to the
752 total solid contents of anammox EPS and pristine granules (TS_{EPS} and $\text{TS}_{\text{granules}}$,
753 respectively).

754

755 **Figure 3** - Experimental adsorption isotherm curves and related fits via Langmuir and
756 Freundlich models (in continuous and dotted lines, respectively) for anammox EPS (full
757 markers, black lines) and pristine granules (empty markers, red lines) towards Pb^{2+} (**a**),
758 Cu^{2+} (**b**), Ni^{2+} (**c**) and Zn^{2+} (**d**). Adsorption capacities (Q_e , mg/g) are related to the total
759 solid contents of anammox EPS and pristine granules (TS_{EPS} and $\text{TS}_{\text{granules}}$,
760 respectively).

761

762 **Figure 4** - Metal cations released and adsorbed (in meq/gTS) by anammox EPS (**a**) and
763 pristine granules (**b**) during heavy metal biosorption tests at $C_0=500$ mg/L (i.e., 2.58,
764 7.76, 8.59 and 6.55 mM for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , respectively).

765

766 **Figure 1**

767

768 **Figure 2**

769

770 **Figure 3**

771

772 **Figure 4**

773

774 **Table 1** - Adsorption capacity of anammox EPS in single- and multi-metal biosorption tests
775 ($C_0=40 \text{ mgM}^{2+}/\text{L}$).

	Adsorption capacity (mg/gTS_{EPS})	
	<i>Multi-metal sorption</i>	<i>Single-metal sorption</i>
Pb ²⁺	5.56	7.83
Cu ²⁺	4.45	4.35
Ni ²⁺	2.36	3.06
Zn ²⁺	2.43	1.07

776

777 **Table 2** – Elemental analysis of EPS-Pb/Cu composite aggregates (precipitated in single-metal
778 biosorption test at $C_0=500$ mg/L) detected by energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS).
779 Average values \pm standard deviations (n. 4 and 3 points of analysis for composite EPS-Pb and
780 EPS-Cu aggregates, respectively).

Composite EPS-Pb aggregates			Composite EPS-Cu aggregates		
C	40.51 ± 5.63	Weight%	C	53.55 ± 2.47	Weight%
	66.12 ± 7.38	Atomic%		63.90 ± 1.44	Atomic%
O	34.59 ± 4.79	Weight%	O	38.17 ± 0.04	Weight%
	30.80 ± 5.36	Atomic%		34.22 ± 0.85	Atomic%
Pb	9.85 ± 7.84	Weight%	Cu	8.28 ± 2.42	Weight%
	1.54 ± 0.63	Atomic%		1.88 ± 0.59	Atomic%
O:C	0.495 ± 0.104	mol/C-mol _{EPS}	O:C	0.536 ± 0.025	mol/C-mol _{EPS}
Pb:C	0.023 ± 0.007	mol/C-mol _{EPS}	Cu:C	0.029 ± 0.007	mol/C-mol _{EPS}
Pb:EPS	0.171 ± 0.056	g/gTS _{EPS}	Cu:EPS	0.068 ± 0.023	g/gTS _{EPS}

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